

A REFINED THEORY WITH THE SUPERPARAMETRIC ELEMENT
FOR LAMINATED COMPOSITE-SANDWICH SHELLS

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ABSTRACT

Recently developed refined theory is used for the analysis of laminated anisotropic sandwich shells with the superparametric shell element. The displacement field is based on the Taylor's series expansion of the generic displacements and it accounts for the parabolic variation of inplane displacements and transverse displacement through the laminate thickness. In addition to the present theory, a first order shear deformation shell theory hitherto used, is developed and the significant difference in the results of both the theories is noted for the laminate with high stiff top and bottom layers and very soft middle core. The finite element formulation presented here in conjunction with the higher order shear deformation theory has a wide range of applicability for plate and shell type structures with arbitrary geometry, loading and boundary conditions.

KEYWORDS: Anisotropy; Finite element analysis; Refined theory; Sandwich construction; Shells; Thick laminate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sandwich materials consisting of a low density core with stiff skins offer considerable potential for weight saving in aeronautical, mechanical, structural and marine applications. An ideal structural sandwich material consists of a thick sheet of light weight material, with a thin sheet of much stiffer, stronger material attached to each face. The skin resists in-plane forces and bending moments, whilst the core resists transverse shear forces. The core must be stiff enough in shear to prevent the skins sliding over each other, and in compression to keep the skins the correct distance apart. The analysis and design methods needed to analyse sandwich structures under transverse loads depend on the relative importance of core shear deformations during bending. When the core is stiff in shear, shear deformations in bending are negligible and classical bending theory may be used with an appropriate value for the flexural rigidity. When the core is flexible in shear, shear deformations may be significant and contribute structural deflections during transverse loading. In this case, classical bending analysis for beams, plates and shell structures requires modification to include thickness shear effects.

For a more rigorous analysis modified design analysis methods which include core shear flexibility are available [1], and these methods are necessary for certain aerospace sandwich materials with very stiff skins. In aerospace sandwich structures, design analysis is being carried out using finite element and other computer aided design methods in which details of the stress distribution through the core and skins of the structure are examined in terms of the applied loads [2]. A detailed historical review is given in the books by Allen [1] and Plantema [3] and in two papers by Habip [4,5]. Recently, Mallikarjuna and Kant [6-11] emphasised on establishing the credibility of higher-order shear deformable theories with C^0 finite element for static and dynamic analysis and in obtaining solutions to general laminated composite-sandwich problems. This paper specifically deals with the application of the superparametric element and

a refined theory for predictions of cross-sectional warping in the anisotropic sandwich laminated shells.

2. FINITE ELEMENT DISCRETIZATION

Element with a higher degree of interpolation on the coordinates than on the displacements is called in general superparametric element. The element formulation and the present theory are quite general and can be used for elements with any number of nodes, prominently among them being the quadratic and cubic Serendipity and Lagrangian elements.

2.1 Element Geometry A typical shell element and the nodal, local and global coordinates (v_{1i}, v_{2i}, v_{3i}) , (x', y', z') and (x, y, z) respectively, are shown in Figure 1. At each point of the shell, the direction z' is normal to the midsurface which is being obtained by the cross product of the curvilinear coordinates ξ and η directions ($\vec{z}' = \vec{v}_\xi \times \vec{v}_\eta$). The global coordinates of pairs of points on the top and bottom surface at each node are usually input to define the element geometry. Alternatively, the mid-surface nodal coordinates and the corresponding directional thickness can be furnished. The external faces of the element are curved, while the sections across the thickness are generated by straight lines. A relationship between the Cartesian coordinates of any point of the shell and the curvilinear co-ordinates can be written in the form

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^{NN} N_i(\xi, \eta) \begin{pmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \\ z_i \end{pmatrix}_{\text{mid}} + \sum_{i=1}^{NN} N_i(\xi, \eta) z' \vec{v}_{3i} \quad (1)$$

where $N_i(\xi, \eta)$ is a shape function taking a value of unity at the nodes i and zero of all other nodes, NN denotes the number of nodes in an element, (x_i, y_i, z_i) are the midsurface global coordinates of the i^{th} nodal point which is computed by taking average of the top and bottom nodal coordinates, v_{3i} is the vector whose length is the shell thickness.

2.2 Displacement Model The element displacements are completely defined by the midsurface nodal displacements u_i, v_i, w_i in the x, y and z global coordinate directions, and the rotations β_i, α_i and γ_i , which are about v_{1i}, v_{2i} and v_{3i} axes respectively. The parameters β_i^*, α_i^* and γ_i^* , are the corresponding higher-order terms in the Taylor's series expansion. The vectors v_{1i}, v_{2i} and v_{3i} are being mutually perpendicular to each other. The displacements at any point (ξ, η, z') can be expressed in terms of the nodal displacements as

$$\begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^{NN} N_i(\xi, \eta) \begin{pmatrix} u_i \\ v_i \\ w_i \end{pmatrix} + \sum_{i=1}^{NN} N_i(\xi, \eta) z' \underline{\mu}_i \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_i \\ -\beta_i \\ -\gamma_i \end{pmatrix} \\ + \sum_{i=1}^{NN} N_i(\xi, \eta) z'^2 \underline{\mu}_i \begin{pmatrix} * \\ \alpha_i \\ * \\ -\beta_i \\ * \\ -\gamma_i \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $\underline{\mu}_i$ is a matrix of direction cosines of $\vec{v}_{1i}, \vec{v}_{2i}$ and \vec{v}_{3i} which is given in Equation (3a). The element coordinate definition given by the relation (1) has more degrees of freedom than the definition of the displacements. The element is therefore of the super-parametric kind.

2.3 Relation Between Nodal, Local and Global Coordinate Systems The displacements in the nodal coordinate system can be expressed in terms of global coordinate system by

Figure 1a - Local and global coordinates.

Figure 1b - A typical nine noded shell element.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u_i \\ v_i \\ w_i \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} l_{1i} & m_{1i} & n_{1i} \\ l_{2i} & m_{2i} & n_{2i} \\ l_{3i} & m_{3i} & n_{3i} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{Bmatrix}; \begin{Bmatrix} \beta_i \\ \alpha_i \\ \gamma_i \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} l_{1i} & m_{1i} & n_{1i} \\ l_{2i} & m_{2i} & n_{2i} \\ l_{3i} & m_{3i} & n_{3i} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \theta_x \\ \theta_y \\ \theta_z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3a)$$

Similarly, the displacements in the local coordinate system can also be expressed in terms of global coordinate system,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u' \\ v' \\ w' \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{l}_1 & \bar{m}_1 & \bar{n}_1 \\ \bar{l}_2 & \bar{m}_2 & \bar{n}_2 \\ \bar{l}_3 & \bar{m}_3 & \bar{n}_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{Bmatrix}; \begin{Bmatrix} \theta_{x'} \\ \theta_{y'} \\ \theta_{z'} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{l}_1 & \bar{m}_1 & \bar{n}_1 \\ \bar{l}_2 & \bar{m}_2 & \bar{n}_2 \\ \bar{l}_3 & \bar{m}_3 & \bar{n}_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \theta_x \\ \theta_y \\ \theta_z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3b)$$

These individual transformation matrices are orthogonal, hence, the displacements in local coordinate system can be expressed in terms of the nodal coordinate system.

It should be noted that for higher order degrees-of-freedom, the same matrix of direction cosines which are used in Equations (3a) and (3b) are employed, and the relation between nodal, local and global coordinate systems is established in the same way as explained above.

2.4 Strain-Displacement Matrix The relationship between the strains at any point within a laminate and the corresponding deformations are the functions of the assumed displacement field. The strain components in terms of the local system of axes x', y', z' (where z' is normal to the $\xi\eta$ -plane) are given by

$$\underline{\epsilon}' = [\epsilon_{x'}, \epsilon_{y'}, \epsilon_{z'}, \gamma_{x'y'}, \gamma_{y'z'}, \gamma_{x'z'}]^T \quad (4a)$$

$$= \left[\frac{\partial u'}{\partial x'}, \frac{\partial v'}{\partial y'}, \frac{\partial w'}{\partial z'}, \frac{\partial u'}{\partial y'} + \frac{\partial v'}{\partial x'}, \frac{\partial v'}{\partial z'} + \frac{\partial w'}{\partial y'}, \frac{\partial u'}{\partial z'} + \frac{\partial w'}{\partial x'} \right]^T \quad (4b)$$

where u', v', w' are the displacement components in the local system.

In C^0 finite element, the continuum displacement vector within the element is discretized such that

$$\underline{\delta}' = \sum_{i=1}^{NN} N_i \underline{\delta}_i = \underline{N} \underline{d}_e \quad (5a)$$

in which $\underline{\delta}_i$ is the generalized displacement vector corresponding to the i^{th} node of an element, \underline{N} is the shape function matrix and is given by

$$\underline{N} = [N_1, N_2, \dots, N_{NN}] \quad (5b)$$

and \underline{d}_e is the element displacement vector and is written as

$$\underline{d}_e = [\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_{NN}]^T \quad (5c)$$

The generalized strain vector $\underline{\epsilon}'$ at any point within an element in the local coordinate system can be expressed by the following relationship:

$$\bar{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}}' = \sum_{i=1}^{NN} \underline{\underline{B}}_i \underline{\underline{\delta}}_i \quad (6a)$$

where

$$\bar{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}}' = \left[\varepsilon_{x_0}, \varepsilon_{y_0}, \varepsilon_{z_0}, \gamma_{x'y'_0}, \chi_x, \chi_y, \chi_z, \chi_{x'y'}, \right. \\ \left. \varepsilon_{x_0}^*, \varepsilon_{y_0}^*, \varepsilon_{z_0}^*, \gamma_{x'y'_0}^*, \gamma_{x'z'_0}, \gamma_{y'z'_0}, \phi_x, \phi_y, \gamma_{x'z'_0}^*, \gamma_{y'z'_0}^* \right]^T \quad (6b)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\delta}}_i = \left[u_i, v_i, w_i, \alpha_i, \beta_i, \gamma_i, \alpha_i^*, \beta_i^*, \gamma_i^* \right]^T \quad (6c)$$

$\underline{\underline{B}}$ is the strain-displacement matrix defined in terms of the displacement derivatives with respect to the local Cartesian coordinates x' , y' and z' .

2.5 Rigidity Matrix Although for the most general cases of anisotropy the number of independent elastic constants is 21, this number is considerably reduced if the material internal composition possesses symmetry of any kind [12]. A state of anisotropy which possesses three mutually orthogonal planes of symmetry at each layer is assumed. Fibre-reinforced composite structures almost invariably possess this kind of symmetry, with the mid-layer surface being a symmetric plane at each point. If the reference system of orthogonal axes (x', y', z') is parallel to the principal material axes (1,2,3), the following stress-strain relationships can be obtained:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_3 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_3 \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{Bmatrix} \tau_{12} \\ \tau_{23} \\ \tau_{13} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{44} & & \\ & C_{55} & \\ & & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{12} \\ \gamma_{23} \\ \gamma_{13} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (7a)$$

in which,

$$C_{11} = E_1 (1 - \nu_{32} \nu_{23}) / \Delta, \quad C_{12} = E_2 (\nu_{12} + \nu_{13} \nu_{32}) / \Delta, \\ C_{13} = E_3 (\nu_{13} + \nu_{12} \nu_{23}) / \Delta, \quad C_{22} = E_2 (1 - \nu_{31} \nu_{13}) / \Delta, \quad C_{23} = E_3 (\nu_{23} + \nu_{13} \nu_{21}) / \Delta, \\ C_{33} = E_3 (1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21}) / \Delta, \quad \Delta = 1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21} - \nu_{23} \nu_{32} - \nu_{31} \nu_{13} - 2 \nu_{12} \nu_{23} \nu_{31}, \\ C_{44} = G_{12}, \quad C_{55} = G_{23}, \quad C_{66} = G_{13} \quad (7b)$$

If the principal axes of anisotropy 1,2 do not coincide with the reference axes x' , y' , but are rotated by a certain angle θ , then the new elasticity matrix $\underline{\underline{Q}}$ is determined from the following transformation [6,13],

$$\underline{\underline{Q}} = \underline{\underline{T}}^{-1} \underline{\underline{C}} \underline{\underline{T}}^{-1T} \quad (7c)$$

in which the superscript T and -1 represent the transpose and an inverse of a matrix respectively, and inverse of the transformation matrix is obtained by replacing θ by $-\theta$ in $\underline{\underline{T}}$. The constitutive relation for any layer in the ($x'-y'$) system of the form:

$$\underline{\underline{\sigma}}' = \underline{\underline{Q}} \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}' \quad (8a)$$

where

$$\underline{\sigma}' = [\sigma_{x'}, \sigma_{y'}, \sigma_{z'}, \tau_{x'y'}, \tau_{y'z'}, \tau_{x'z'}]^T \quad (8b)$$

$$\underline{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{Q}_{ij} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{Q}_{lm} \end{bmatrix} \begin{matrix} i,j = 1,2,3,4 \\ l,m = 5,6 \end{matrix} \quad (8c)$$

The constitutive relations involving inplane forces, bending moments and shear forces are defined as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_{x'} & N_{y'} & N_{z'} & N_{x'y'} \\ M_{x'} & M_{y'} & M_{z'} & M_{x'y'} \\ N_{x'}^* & N_{y'}^* & 0 & N_{x'y'}^* \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{L=1}^n \int_{h_L}^{h_{L+1}} [\sigma_{x'}, \sigma_{y'}, \sigma_{z'}, \tau_{x'y'}] \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ z' \\ z'^2 \end{bmatrix} dz' \quad (9a)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} Q_{x'} & S_{x'} & Q_{x'}^* \\ Q_{y'} & S_{y'} & Q_{y'}^* \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{L=1}^n \int_{h_L}^{h_{L+1}} \begin{bmatrix} \tau_{x'z'} \\ \tau_{y'z'} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & z' & z'^2 \end{bmatrix} dz' \quad (9b)$$

After integration, these relations are written in a matrix form which defines the stress-resultant/strain relations of the laminate:

$$\bar{\sigma}' = \underline{D} \bar{\xi}' \quad (10a)$$

in which

$$\bar{\sigma}' = [N_{x'}, N_{y'}, N_{z'}, N_{x'y'}, M_{x'}, M_{y'}, M_{z'}, M_{x'y'}, N_{x'}^*, N_{y'}^*, N_{x'y'}^*, Q_{x'}, Q_{y'}, S_{x'}, S_{y'}, Q_{x'}^*, Q_{y'}^*]^T \quad (10b)$$

$\bar{\xi}'$ is a vector of mid-surface strains and is defined in Equation (6b), and \underline{D} is the rigidity matrix which can be written as

$$\underline{D} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{D}_{mb} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{D}_s \end{bmatrix} \quad (10c)$$

where \underline{D}_{mb} contains the membrane, coupling between inplane and bending, and flexural rigidity terms, and \underline{D}_s is the shear rigidity matrix.

$$\underline{D}_{mb} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{Q}_{ij}H_1 & \underline{Q}_{ij}H_2 & \underline{Q}_{pq}H_3 \\ \underline{Q}_{ij}H_2 & \underline{Q}_{ij}H_3 & \underline{Q}_{pq}H_4 \\ \underline{Q}_{qp}H_3 & \underline{Q}_{qp}H_4 & \underline{Q}_{rs}H_5 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } \underline{D}_s = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{Q}_{ml}H_1 & \underline{Q}_{ml}H_2 & \underline{Q}_{ml}H_3 \\ \underline{Q}_{ml}H_2 & \underline{Q}_{ml}H_3 & \underline{Q}_{ml}H_4 \\ \underline{Q}_{ml}H_3 & \underline{Q}_{ml}H_4 & \underline{Q}_{ml}H_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10d)$$

$i,j = 1,2,3,4$; $p = 1,2,3,4$; $q = 1,2,4$; $r,s = 1,2,4$; $m,l = 6,5$

In the above relations, L defines the L^{th} layer, n is the number of layers in a laminate and

$$H_n' = \frac{1}{n} (h_{L+1}^{n'} - h_L^{n'}) ; n' = 1,2,3,4,5 \quad (10e)$$

2.6 Stiffness Matrix The size of the element stiffness matrix depends on the number of nodes in the element and the degrees of freedom per node. In the present model, size of the element matrix is $9NN \times 9NN$, where NN is the number of nodes in an element. Since the strain-displacement matrix \underline{B} and the rigidity matrix \underline{D} are obtained in local coordinates x', y', z' , the same matrices should be used for the computation of element stiffness matrix. Here the transformation is derived based on the concept that during any virtual displacement, the resulting increment in strain energy density must be the same regardless of the coordinate system in which it is computed. Hence the stiffness matrix is given by

$$\underline{K} = \int_A \underline{B}^T \underline{D} \underline{B} dA = \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \underline{B}^T \underline{D} \underline{B} |\underline{J}| d\xi d\eta \quad (11)$$

As the rigidity matrix specifies the properties of the cross-section, the integration for the stiffness matrix is over the midsurface of the shell. The coordinate Jacobian \underline{J} is evaluated at the Gauss points lying on the shell midsurface.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to demonstrate the accuracy of the present theory and to show the effect of cross-sectional warping in the composite-sandwich structures, the geometric and material properties given in Table 1 were used. In addition to the present refined higher order shear deformation theory (HOST), the program was developed for first-order shear deformation theory (FOST) with five degrees of freedom i.e. v, w, θ_x, θ_y . Due to lack of well accepted coefficients for anisotropic composite-sandwich structures, the transverse shear energy term in FOST is corrected using a multiplier 5/6 for all the materials except for the core of a sandwich shell where a coefficient of unity has been used.

TABLE 1 GEOMETRIC AND MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Principal radii of curvature of the middle surface ($R_1 = R_2 = R$) = varying
Arc length $a = b = 32.0$ cm.

Intensity of uniformly distributed load $q = 1$ N/cm²

Face Sheets (Graphite/ epoxy prepreg system)

$E_1 = 1.308 \times 10^7$ N/cm², $E_2 = E_3 = 1.06 \times 10^6$ N/cm²

$G_{12} = G_{13} = 6.0 \times 10^5$ N/cm², $G_{23} = 3.9 \times 10^5$ N/cm²,

$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.28$, $\nu_{23} = 0.34$

Core (U.S. Commercial aluminium honey-comb, 1/4 in. cell size,
0.003in. foil)

$G_{23} = 1.772 \times 10^4$ N/cm², $G_{13} = 5.206 \times 10^4$ N/cm²

To investigate the numerical convergence, many examples were solved by using 8-node Serendipity and 9-node Lagrangian elements with different mesh size and numerical integration schemes. In the example presented here a 9-noded element with reduced integration Gauss quadrature rule and 4×4 mesh is employed. It should be noted that, if the radius of curvature is more i.e., for $R/a < 1.0$, further refinement of mesh size is required. Due to limitation of space here, those results are not presented.

A clamped composite-sandwich spherical shell (0/45/core/60/90) subjected to a uniformly distributed load on the shell midsurface is analysed. Thickness of each stiff layer is 0.05h and core material is 0.8h. Table 2 presents the centre transverse deflection for different ratios of radius of curvature-to-arc length and arc length-to-thickness of the spherical shell. It is observed that, the maximum difference between FOST and HOST is about 18% in the case of moderately thick shell ($a/h=10$) and about 1% in thin shells ($a/h=100$). This is due to realistic representation of the cross-sectional deformation and consideration of the complete stress strain law in the present higher order shear deformation theory.

Table 2 CENTER DEFLECTION ($w \times 10^{-4}$ cm.) OF A CLAMPED UNSYMMETRIC COMPOSITE-SANDWICH SPHERICAL SHELL.

R/a	a/h	0°/45°/core/60°/90°	
		10	100
10 ³⁰	HOST	7.0894	3218.3
	FOST	5.7593 (-18.7)	3212.4 (0.18)
10	HOST	6.9199	1355.2
	FOST	5.6097 (-18.9)	1354.5 (0.05)
5	HOST	6.4214	459.99
	FOST	5.2086 (-18.9)	460.06 (-0.01)
2	HOST	4.2027	63.568
	FOST	3.4677 (-17.5)	63.390 (0.28)
1	HOST	1.8481	15.751
	FOST	1.5809 (-14.4)	15.561 (1.22)
0.7	HOST	1.0236	9.2800
	FOST	0.9325 (-8.89)	9.1635 (1.27)

Values in brackets indicate the percentage difference with respect to HOST.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A refined general shell theory is developed in conjunction with the superparametric element for analysis of isotropic, orthotropic and anisotropic composite and sandwich plate and shell structures. The superparametric shell element with four noded linear, eight/nine noded quadratic and twelve/sixteen noded cubic, Serendipity/Lagrangian shape functions can be employed. The evaluations using the present higher order theory show considerable warping of the transverse cross-section for composite-sandwich laminates. This true behavior is not possible to model with a first order shear deformation theory.

An extension of the present work to reduce the higher-order degrees of freedom, and express them in terms of primary degrees of freedom $u, v, w, \theta_x, \theta_y, \theta_z$ for making it compatible with the general purpose program (GPP) is currently under investigation at the Department of Civil Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, India.

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